

Factors influencing online shopping behavior of University students in Hanoi, Vietnam: A model and empirical study

Huong Thanh Vu, Chinh Duc Hoang, Thao Hoa Thien Le

Faculty of International Business and Economics, University of Economics and Business,
Vietnam National University

corresponding e-mail: [huongvt\[at\]vnu\(dot\)edu{d}vn](mailto:huongvt[at]vnu(dot)edu{d}vn)

address: Huong Thanh Vu, Faculty of International Business and Economics, Vietnam National University - Hanoi,
144 Xuan Thuy, Cau Giay, Ha Noi, Vietnam

Abstract: By adopting selectively two classical models of consumer behavior, Theory of Rational Action and Technology Acceptance Model, and combining with two other factors, the paper proposed a model of six factors including Attitude, Perceived Risk, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Subjective Norm and Web Quality to assess determinants of university students' online shopping behavior in Hanoi, Vietnam. The model was assessed through Explanatory Factor Analysis, regression analysis and independent sample test based on data collected from 289 university students in Hanoi, Vietnam. The results showed that Perceived Usefulness plays the most important role in determining students' online shopping behavior, followed by Web Quality and Attitude. There is also a difference in online shopping behavior between the third-year and first-year students, and between the third-year and second-year students. From these results, the paper drew out implications to support E-commerce enterprises to attract more university students to shop online, and strengthen the development of E-commerce in Vietnam

JEL Classifications: D10, D12, L81

Keywords: Online shopping behavior, E-commerce, students, Hanoi, Vietnam

Citation: Thanh Vu, H., Duc Hoang, C., Hoa Thien Le, T., Minh Do, T. (2019). Factors influencing online shopping behavior of University students in Hanoi, Vietnam: A model and empirical study. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 15(4), 573-592.

1. Introduction

In the emerging context of Industrial Revolution 4.0, E-commerce has played an increasingly important role as a strong momentum for the social and economic development. Thanks to widespread application of E-Commerce, enterprises can go beyond spatial limitation to approach wider markets.

In Vietnam, E-commerce was formally introduced in 1997 and then started to grow strongly in 2016, when the government adopted Master Plan for E-commerce Development in 2016 - 2020 period (VECOM, 2018). In addition, together with the increased Internet penetration, expanded use of smartphone and growing popularity of social media, the scale of E-commerce market in Vietnam has strongly developed. In 2016, total sales of Business to Consumer (B2C) E-commerce in Vietnam reached about USD 5 billion compared to only USD 2.97 billion in 2014 (VECITA, 2017). In the period 2013-2017, with the growth rate of 33%, Vietnam has emerged as one of the most dynamic and fast-paced E-commerce markets in Southeast Asia (EVBN, 2018). Vietnam's consumers have so far become more familiar with a wide range of E-commerce websites, both foreign and domestic origins, such as eBay, Amazon, Lazada, Tiki, Shopee, Sendo, and Adayroi. Over the past five years, the Vietnamese government has also made great

effort to create favorable environment for the development of E-commerce industry and at the same time promulgated policies to protect the online shoppers.

E-commerce has been becoming an inseparable part of the Vietnamese's daily life, especially for the young population. The estimated percentage of online shoppers among Internet users has rapidly increased since 2014 and reached 65% by 2016 (VECITA, 2017). Among the online shoppers participated in a survey by VECITA (2017), the young people from 18 to 25 years old accounted for 49%, of which 28% are university students whose time of using Internet is from 5 - 7 hours per day on average. Millennials which accounted for 30% of Vietnam's population, or approximately 29 million people in 2017 are also currently the largest group of online shoppers in Vietnam (EVBN, 2018). The Vietnamese young customers have increasingly become the appropriate subjects of online shopping (Iran Phi Hoang et al., 2015) because of their strength in quicker access to Internet, more frequent use of smartphone, and more rapid absorption of changes in technology compared to the elderly people. As a result, the participation of digitally savvy youth especially university students has made E-commerce market in Vietnam more dynamic and busier.

However, the youth in Vietnam tends to prefer shopping online on foreign websites such as Amazon and eBay to domestic ones, and their trust in online shopping is still limited (Nguyen & Le, 2014). Income of the youth, especially university students, is also a factor hindering their online shopping activities. In consideration of the rapid development of E-commerce and the importance of the youth, especially university students in E-commerce in Vietnam, this paper aims at exploring factors influencing online shopping behavior of university students in Hanoi, Vietnam and providing some suggestions for E-commerce enterprises to attract more youth customers, contributing to promote the development of E-commerce industry in Vietnam.

2. Literature review

2.1. E-commerce development in Vietnam

Vietnam is assessed to be a potential market for E-commerce development with favorable conditions in policies, upward trend in online shopping, increase in domestic competition, and improvement in digital landscape.

The Vietnamese government has made substantial efforts to develop E-commerce industry. After the success of implementation of Master Plan for E-commerce Development in 2011-2015 period, Vietnam approved Master Plan for E-commerce Development in 2016-2020 period with the objectives to promote E-commerce infrastructure, expand market scale, and strengthen businesses' and governmental agencies' application of E-commerce. In order to achieve these objectives, a series of actions and measures have been undertaken. In 2017, Vietnam promulgated Decree No. 16/CT-TTg regarding "Improving capability to access to Industrial Revolution 4.0" to enable Vietnam to take advantage of digitalization and information technology into E-commerce development (VECOM, 2018). Vietnam has paid attention in exploiting cloud computing, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Augmented Reality (VR), and Internet of Things (IoT) to construct modern business models. The tax administration for E-commerce has also been improved (VECOM, 2018), and a national E-commerce payment system and integrated E-payment solutions will be set up by 2020 (EVBN, 2020).

Although being relatively new, Vietnam's E-commerce industry is on the verge of explosion as the revenue of B2C E-commerce exceeded USD 5 billion in 2016, equivalent to an increase of 23% compared to the year 2015 (VECITA, 2017) and reached a growth rate of 32.3% in the period 2013-2017 (EVBN, 2018). Clothes, footwear, cosmetics, technological and electronic devices, and household items are most frequently purchased by online customers. The Vietnamese customers are more interested in shopping through Internet, and suppliers have at the same time focused more on E-commerce to attract new targeted buyers (VECITA, 2017).

As the Vietnamese E-commerce market has stepped into the period of rapid development, foreign and domestic E-commerce enterprises have been in a fiercer competition to capture market shares in Vietnam. Google became a member of Vietnam E-commerce Association (VECOM) in 2012 (VECOM, 2012), while Alibaba and eBay have set up partnership with official representatives in Vietnam in 2017 and 2018, respectively (Minh, 2017; Balfour, 2018). Besides foreign E-commerce platforms such as Lazada, Zalora, and Shopee, local E-marketplaces such as Tiki, Sendo, The gioi di dong and Adayroi are joining the E-commerce industry, creating a dynamic, fast-growing and highly competitive E-commerce market in Vietnam (EVBN, 2018).

One important condition for E-commerce development is digital landscape, which has been strengthened in Vietnam in the last ten years. According to EVBN (2018), in 2017, Vietnam had approximately 52 million Internet users, equivalent to a 54% Internet penetration rate, which is above the global average of 46.5%. Vietnam's smartphone penetration rate is high, reaching 72% in both 2016 and 2017. Its share of mobile traffic increased by 26%, which was the highest rate among Southeast Asian nations in 2017. Vietnam merchants also led the way in the conversion rate - the percentage of website visits that convert into a product chase - which was 30% higher than the average of Southeast Asian nations (Iprice Insights, 2017).

However, E-commerce development in Vietnam has coped with a lot of challenges. The Internet fixed connection speed as well as mobile Internet connection speed were only 24.8mbps and 20.3mbps in January 2018, respectively, which were quite low compared to the world average of 40.7mbps and 21.3mbps (Kemp, 2018). Information security is another aspect that needs improvement. A survey on the websites of twelve VECOM's member corporations found that 17% of them had severe security hole in which customers' personal data could be illegally accessed by other users (VSEC, 2017).

Other risks include the leakage of online transaction information and the attack of hackers to E-commerce enterprises' computer systems to control the data. The issue in information security has partly resulted in low trust on E-commerce and the high use of cash in E-commerce transactions (EVBN, 2018). According to VECITA (2017) and EVBN (2018), 91% of the Vietnamese consumers used cash in E-commerce transaction in 2015 and 89% in 2016. The development of online payment system is also inadequate with only 16% of corporations accepting payment by cards in 2015 (VECOM, 2016) and only 2% of adults aged more than 15 possessing a credit card in online shopping by January 2018 (Kemp, 2018). Human resources specialized in information technology and E-commerce have been in shortage in Vietnam. According to a survey by VECOM (2018), only 30% of surveyed enterprises had employees specialized in developing E-commerce and 31% had difficulties in hiring E-commerce employees in 2017.

2.2. Factors influencing online shopping behavior in Vietnam

There are several studies examining domestic online shoppers' behavior in Vietnam. By using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) developed by Davis (1985) and Davis (1989) as the theoretical premise, Duong (2012) found out that the two main factors influencing online shopping decision in Hue city are "Perceived Usefulness" and "Perceived Ease of Use", while Dang (2014) pointed out that in Da Nang city, "Consumer's Trust", "Subjective Norm" and "Perceived Ease of Use" influence most the Internet shopping behavior.

Based on the Theory of Planned Behavior constructed by Ajzen (1991), Ha & Nguyen (2016) discovered the role of "Perceived Risks" in determining Vietnamese consumers' intention to shop online. Their research findings showed that "Attitude" and "Perceived Behavioral Control" positively affect online shopping intention whereas "Perceived Risk" negatively influences it. Similar to Ha & Nguyen (2016), by using consumer attitude and behavior model developed in a study by Li & Zhang (2002), Nguyen & Le (2014) indicated that "Perceived Risk" has effects on intention to shop online. Besides, other factors including "Diverse Selection of Goods", "Belief", "Responsiveness of the Site", "the Comfort when Buying" and "Price" also affect the consumers' decision to continue or begin online shopping. Ngo & Gim (2014) found that "Perceived of Economic Benefits", "Perceived of Merchandise" and "Perceived Payment Benefits" have significant effects on consumers' adoption of online shopping. Focusing on the services provided by online organizations, Tran et al. (2017) stated that "Payment Method", "User Interface" and "People Influence" induce the Vietnamese to try online purchase. Social network is another critical aspect that affects online buying decision of the Vietnamese. There is a strong relationship between social network and consumer's trust, by which consumers' participation in social network such as Facebook, Twitter and Go.vn increases the intention to purchase (Vo & Han, 2017).

Review of the past literature shows that a lot of factors affecting Vietnamese online customers' behavior have been examined. However, most of the above factors are related to perception of consumers when shopping online. A number of factors related to the service providers or online infrastructure have been ignored in the past literature. Moreover, the previous studies have mostly focused on general online shoppers. There is virtually no study focusing on the youth in general and the university students in particular while they have played an increasing role in E-commerce development and will shape the future trend of buying online in Vietnam. There is also no study quantifying factors influencing behavior of online shoppers in Hanoi, which is Vietnam's capital city and a location of a large number of universities and students in Vietnam. Hanoi has also been among Top 2 City in Vietnam in term of E-commerce index (VECOM, 2016; VECOM, 2018). Therefore, the paper contributes to the existing literature in two aspects. Firstly, the paper investigates online shopping behaviors of university students in Hanoi, Vietnam. Secondly, the paper quantifies factors affecting online shopping behavior, taking into consideration of other factors besides customers' perception.

3. Methodology and data

3.1. Research model

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) are among the most common models used in previous literature to understand determinants of

consumer behavior in E-commerce industry. In TRA, two factors deciding consumer behavior are “Attitude towards the behavior” and “Subjective Norms about the behavior” (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975; Loudon & Bitta, 1993). Choosing TRA as the reference paradigm, Davis (1985) and Davis (1989) developed TAM, which indicates that “Perceived Usefulness” and “Perceived Ease of Use” are two determinants of technology acceptance behavior.

Applying two models above and extending to include two other factors, the paper proposed a model with six independent factors to evaluate online shopping behavior of students at universities in Hanoi, Vietnam. The model included four factors coming from TRA and TAM, which are Attitude, Subjective Norm, Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use, and two other factors namely Perceived Risk, and Web Quality (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. RESEARCH MODEL

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

3.2. Factors and observed variables

Online Shopping Behavior

Consumer behavior describes how consumers make purchase decision and how they use and dispose goods, services, ideas or experience to satisfy their needs and wants (Kotler & Keller, 2006). Understanding consumer behavior therefore requires integrated knowledge from different sciences including psychology, biology, chemistry and economics.

In this paper, the dependent factor Online Shopping Behavior (BP) of university students in Hanoi, Vietnam was measured in three observed variables ranging from BP1 to BP3

(Table 1). BP revealed students' feeling of joy when shopping online, anticipation of online shopping trend and frequency of online shopping.

TABLE 1. FACTORS AND OBSERVED VARIABLES AFFECTING ONLINE SHOPPING BEHAVIOR OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN VIETNAM

FACTOR	FACTORS AND OBSERVED VARIABLES	CODE
DEPENDENT FACTOR	Online shopping behavior	BP
	- I enjoy shopping online	BP1
	- I think online shopping is an upward trend	BP2
	- I frequently shop online	BP3
INDEPENDENT FACTOR	Attitude towards online shopping	AT
	- I am willing to search for new products on Internet	AT1
	- I trust products when shopping online	AT2
	- I am willing to provide personal information when shopping online	AT3
	- I am willing to make payment in advance immediately after confirming the transaction	AT4
	Subjective Norm	SN
	- My friends and colleagues' opinions affect me when I shop online	SN1
	- My family and relatives' opinions affect me when I shop online	SN2
	- Reviews on website affect me when I shop online	SN3
	- Well-known brands affect me when I shop online	SN4
	Perceived Usefulness	PU
	- I think online shopping saves more time than traditional shopping	PU1
	- I think online shopping saves more money than traditional shopping	PU2
	- I have more choices when shopping online than traditional shopping	PU3
	- I can easily compare product information from different sources when shopping online	PU4
	- I have more preferential treatment when shopping online than traditional shopping	PU5
	Perceived Ease of Use	PE
	- I can shop online at anytime and anywhere whenever Internet is available	PE1
	- I can easily track my online order	PE2
	- I can easily make payment when shopping online	PE3
	Perceived Risk	PR
	- I think that product quality is not as advertised in the web	PR1
	- I think information and services provided are not accurate and factual	PR2
	- I think the online payment is risky and not reliable	PR3
	- I think that my personal information can be used for other purposes	PR4
	- I think complaints and refund will be difficult when shopping online	PR5
	- I think money and goods may be missing due to system errors	PR6
	- I think money and goods may be missing due to defective delivery	PR7
	Web Quality	WQ
	- Websites with fast processing speed make me want to purchase online	WQ1
	- Websites with attractive and clear illustration of products make me want to purchase online	WQ2
	- Websites with detailed and clear information make me want to purchase online	WQ3
	- Websites with distinctive and attractive information make me want to purchase online	WQ4
	- Websites that are user-friendly make me want to purchase online	WQ5
	- The ability to access to websites through a wide range of devices (computers, smartphones, tablets...) makes me want to purchase online	WQ6
	- Websites verified by Vietnam's Ministry of Industry and Trade make me want to purchase online	WQ7

Source: compiled by the authors.

Attitude towards online shopping (AT)

According to Fishbein & Ajzen (1975, p.216), "an attitude represents a person's general feeling of favorableness or unfavorableness toward some stimulus object". Numerous previous studies showed that Attitude is an important factor affecting the behavior to shop online. Thananuraksakul (2007) pointed out that Attitude is the most important factor leading to online purchasing decisions of Thai customers. Exploring online purchasing behavior in India, Jadhav & Khanna (2016) and Khare & Rakesh (2011) had similar findings that Attitude has significant effect on consumer's decision. In two studies conducted by Limayem et al. (2000) and Xu & Paulins (2005), results also showed that Attitude determines behavior of online shoppers. Besides, Hoffman et al. (1999), Chang et al. (2005) and Hansen et al. (2004) indicated that the public will buy products if they have a good attitude towards buying as well as on items. People who already have experience in buying and approaching to E-commerce will have a better attitude towards online shopping.

In the paper, Attitude (AT) factor included four observed variables from AT1 to AT4, representing students' belief and willingness to make online purchase from their prior experience (Table 1).

Subjective Norm (SN)

Subjective Norm refers to "the person's perception that most people who are important to him think he should or should not perform the behavior in question" (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975, p. 302). Therefore, Subjective Norm illustrates social factors or subjects that possibly affect an individual's online shopping behavior such as family, media and friend (Limayem et al., 2000). In recent years, with the widespread use of online shopping services, online product reviews from customers, experts or even automated recommendation systems are increasingly available, affecting considerably on consumers' online shopping behavior. By using 1,587 reviews from Amazon.com, Mudambi & Schuff (2010) found that a useful comment can strongly promote customers' purchasing decision. This conclusion is confirmed by Limayem et al. (2000) in a study that collected data from 705 consumers and indicated that Subjective Norm, Attitude, and Beliefs influence online shopping decision.

Subjective norm (SN) factor in this paper therefore was constructed to analyze what source of reference affecting students when they make an online purchase decision. SN was measured in four attributes from SN1 to SN4 (Table 1), including for sources of references namely friends and colleagues, family and relatives, reviews on website and well-known brands.

Perceived Usefulness (PU)

Perceived Usefulness is understood as "the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance" (David, 1995, p. 26). When an individual is aware of usefulness of applying online shopping, he or she will have more motives to use this trading platform. Koufaris (2002) and Gefen & Straub (2000) pointed out that Perceived Usefulness strongly predicts intention to undertake online shopping. Moon & Kim (2001) had the similar finding that Perceived Usefulness is important to user's perceptions and intention to purchase online.

In the paper, five observed variables making up Perceived Usefulness (PU) factor ranged from PU1 to PU5 (Table 1). This factor referred as to the usefulness of shopping online in comparison with traditional shopping.

Perceived Ease of Use (PE)

Perceived Ease of Use is defined as the extent to which an individual believes that the use of a system would not take effort to learn and get acquainted (Davis, 1985). Several studies showed that Perceived Ease of Use affects online shopping decision. Moon & Kim (2001) indicated that Perceived Ease of Use is a determinant of shopping through Internet while Jadhav & Khanna (2016) proved that this factor together with Availability, Low Price, Promotion and Customer Services are main factors influencing online shopping behavior of college students in India.

Perceived Ease of Use (PE) factor in the paper referred to the ease and convenience of shopping online, and was broken down into three attributes from PE1 to PE3 (Table 1).

Perceived Risk (PR)

Numerous studies have shown that online shopping decision is affected by Perceived Risk. As defined by Cox & Rich (1964) and Lee et al. (2001), Perceived Risk is the overall amount of uncertainty and anxiety perceived by a consumer in a particular goods and services when they purchase online. Hoffman et al. (1999), Bhatnagar et al. (2000), Smith & Rupp (2003) and Kim et al. (2008) pointed out that many people are reluctant to make online purchases because they are concerned about the financial and privacy infringement risks. Online shoppers fear that their personal information can be sold to other businesses and the credit card information can be leaked. Product risk is another concern of online shoppers. Teo (2002) indicated that most consumers worry about the risk of buying low quality goods because they cannot touch or feel them directly, the images of goods on the web might be different from their actual images and the sellers do not provide enough information about the products on the web. Besides, the consumers are apprehensive about extended delivery time and being unable to return the goods if they are faulty or cannot function as expected (Bhatnagar et al., 2000). In case of being able to return the goods, consumers may bear the cost of shipping and handling (Lee et al., 2001). Because of above perceived risks, consumers may waste time, money and effort in shopping online.

Perceived Risk (PR) factor in the paper was measure in seven attributes from PR1 to PR7, covering specific risks that were related to product, privacy infringement, payment, system security and delivery (Table 1).

Web quality (WQ)

Song & Zahedi (2001) attempted to evaluate how web design in E-Commerce affects behavior of online shoppers. They broke down web design into five groups of elements including promotion, service, informational interpersonal influence, self-efficacy and resource facilitation. Their research findings showed that all of the above elements significantly and positively affect consumer online shopping behavior. In a study examining Thai's online purchasing behavior, Thananuraksakul (2007) pointed out that consumers do not want to buy online if the website lacks of product information and images, and contains a lot of advertising and alerts. In the same vein, Zhang & Dran

(2000) showed that website design feature such as information content, organization of information content, visual appearance, and credibility can contribute to consumer's satisfaction and dissatisfaction. According to Bhatnagar et al. (2000), webpage loading speed affects online shopping decision while Helander & Khalid (2000) reported that some common problems that cause shoppers not to shop online are inadequate assistance on how to order and lack of product pictures.

In the paper, Web Quality (WQ) factor was measured in seven observed variables from WQ1 to WQ7, and dealt with webpage loading speed, visual appearance, information content, user friendliness, accessibility from multiple devices and E-commerce license.

As a result, in the paper, totally 30 observed variables of 6 above-mentioned factors were selected to assess what influences university students in Hanoi, Vietnam when making online purchase (Table 1).

3.3. Sample and data

Primary data were collected through a well-structured questionnaire that was initially pretested with several university students and then was revised by removing and rewording some unclear questions. The survey was carried out during the period of January - April 2018 through both online basis, where students were invited to visit a specific web-survey, and offline basis, where questionnaires were given to students directly. Totally, 300 answered questionnaires were received, of which 289 were valid respondents. 150 valid respondents were offline.

The participants were required to evaluate the degree of their perception of each observed variable based on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). After checking for scale reliability by using Cronbach's Alpha, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), multiple regression and independent sample test were conducted to appraise the factors affecting university students' online shopping behavior in Hanoi, Vietnam. SPSS and Excel were adopted in the paper to analyze primary data.

TABLE 2. DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SAMPLE

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE	INDICATOR	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Gender	Male	119	41.18
	Female	170	58.82
Grade	1 st year	40	13.84
	2 nd year	139	48.10
	3 rd year	70	24.22
	4 th year	40	13.84
Residence	Inner Hanoi city	78	26.99
	Outskirt of Hanoi city	211	73.01
Monthly expenditure	Under 1 million VND	37	12.80
	1 - 2 million VND	92	31.83
	2 - 3 million VND	105	36.33
	3 - 5 million VND	40	13.84
	Over 5 million VND	15	5.19

Source: Survey results.

Participants are 289 students from around 15 universities in Hanoi, ranging from 1st to 4th year. Of 289 respondents, 170 students are female, accounting for 58.82% and 119 students are male, accounting for 41.18% (Table 2). 78 students live in the inner city while 211 are accommodated in the outskirts of Hanoi city. The 2nd year students participating in the survey accounted for the highest proportion of 48.10%, followed by 3rd year students. Most of the students spent VND 1 - 3 million per month.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Online shopping statistics

The survey results showed that students bought clothes, shoes and fashion accessories online most, followed by books and cosmetics (Figure 2). 37.72% of the students purchased food online. The corresponding figures for electronic devices and entertainment services were 33.22% and 27.68%.

FIGURE 2: GOODS AND SERVICES UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN VIETNAM SHOP ONLINE MOST (%)

Source: Survey's results .

73.70% of the surveyed students said that they used social media platforms to purchase online. 63.67% made online purchase through E-commerce sales websites and 43.6% through E-commerce trading floor. University students in Hanoi, Vietnam believe in the increasing tendency of E-commerce development as 97.58% of the respondents said that they would continue shopping online in the future. However, among the surveyed goods and services, students tend to buy fewer cosmetic products online in the future. The survey results showed that a part of the students had bad experience in buying low-quality cosmetics and underwent some disadvantages in payment and refund. In addition, as cosmetics are related to consumers' health and beauty, and normally at high price, students tend to be more cautious in purchasing these products online.

4.2. Scale reliability analysis

The reliability of questionnaire scale was checked by using Cronbach's Alpha for total 33 individual measurement items, which were divided into a dependent factor and six independent factors (Table 1 above). The paper adopted approach by Nunnally (1978), Peterson (1994) and Slater (1995), by which the acceptable reliability level or Cronbach's Alpha is higher than 0.6 for overall measurements and Corrected item - Total correlation is over 0.3 for individual measurements.

As Cronbach's Alpha values of all seven factors are greater than 0.6 and Corrected item - Total correlation of all individual items are higher than 0.3 (Table 3), the scales can be applied for EFA with reliability. There is only one observed variable AT1 "I am willing to search for new products on Internet" having Corrected item - Total correlation less than 0.3 and Cronbach's Alpha if item deleted increases strongly from 0.652 to 0.729. For this reason, AT1 must be eliminated from the model and 29 remaining observed variables of six independent factors are used for further analysis.

TABLE 3. CRONBACH'S ALPHA RESULTS

FACTORS AND OBSERVED VARIABLES	CODE	CRONBACH'S ALPHA	CORRECTED ITEM - TOTAL CORRELATION	CRONBACH'S ALPHA (if Item deleted)
Online shopping behavior	BP	0.679		
- I enjoy shopping online	BP1		0.485	0.596
- I think online shopping is an upward trend	BP2		0.584	0.462
- I frequently shop online	BP3		0.416	0.679
Attitude towards online shopping	AT	0.652		
- I am willing to search for new products on Internet	AT1		0.170	0.729
- I trust products when shopping online	AT2		0.569	0.491
- I am willing to provide personal information when shopping online	AT3		0.513	0.527
- I am willing to make payment in advance immediately after confirming the transaction	AT4		0.510	0.527
Subjective norm	SN	0.713		
- My friends and colleagues' opinion affect me when I shop online	SN1		0.604	0.584
- My family and relatives' opinion affect me when I shop online	SN2		0.507	0.649
- Reviews on website affect me when I shop online	SN3		0.482	0.661
- Well-known brands affect me when I shop online	SN4		0.418	0.696
Perceived usefulness	PU	0.761		
- I think online shopping saves more time than traditional shopping	PU1		0.443	0.747
- I think online shopping saves more money than traditional shopping	PU2		0.464	0.748
- I have more choices when shopping online than traditional shopping	PU3		0.615	0.687
- I can easily compare product information from different sources	PU4		0.567	0.706
- I have more preferential treatment when	PU5		0.582	0.702

TABLE 3. CRONBACH'S ALPHA RESULTS

FACTORS AND OBSERVED VARIABLES	CODE	CRONBACH'S ALPHA	CORRECTED ITEM - TOTAL CORRELATION	CRONBACH'S ALPHA (if Item deleted)
shopping online than traditional shopping				
Perceived ease of use	PE	0.741		
- I can shop online at anytime and anywhere whenever Internet is available	PE1		0.571	0.651
- I can easily track my online order	PE2		0.603	0.612
- I can easily make payment forward after shopping online	PE3		0.529	0.698
Perceived Risk	PR	0.811		
- I think that product quality is not as advertised in the web	PR1		0.579	0.781
- I think information and services provided are not accurate and factual	PR2		0.543	0.787
- I think the online payment is risky and not reliable	PR3		0.546	0.786
- I think that my personal information can be used for other purposes	PR4		0.464	0.801
- I think complaints and refund will be difficult when shopping online	PR5		0.472	0.799
- I think money and goods may be missing due to system errors	PR6		0.655	0.766
- I think money and goods may be missing due to defective delivery	PR7		0.574	0.781
Web quality	WQ	0.869		
- Websites with fast processing speed make me want to purchase online	WQ1		0.538	0.865
- Websites with attractive and clear illustration of products make me want to purchase online	WQ2		0.734	0.838
- Websites with detailed and clear information make me want to purchase online	WQ3		0.706	0.842
- Websites with distinctive and attractive information make me want to purchase online	WQ4		0.574	0.860
- Websites that are user-friendly make me want to purchase online	WQ5		0.689	0.844
- The ability to access to websites through a wide range of devices (computers, smartphones, tablets...) makes me want to purchase online	WQ6		0.684	0.845
- Websites verified by Vietnam's Ministry of Industry and Trade make me want to purchase online	WQ7		0.599	0.856

Source: compiled by the authors from SPSS results.

4.3. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

The data was examined using principal component analysis as the extraction technique and Varimax as the method of rotation to minimize the number of variables that have large coefficients for the same factor. Conditions for variables to be kept in the model are: (1) factor loading is greater than 0.5. If a variable appears simultaneously in two groups in component matrix with an absolute difference in loading factors higher than 0.3, then the

variable will be retained; (2) Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin or KMO is between 0.5 and 1; (3) Bartlett test is significant; (4) percentage of variance is over 50%; and (5) only the factors having Eigenvalue higher than 1 would be retained in the model as EFA was conducted based on extraction ratio factor.

EFA was implemented six times and totally eight variables were eliminated from research measurements because they did not meet the criteria above. PE1, PE2 and PE3 were removed in the first rotation; SN4 and PU5 in the second rotation; and PR6, PR7 and PR5 in the next three rotations respectively. PE1, PE2, PE3, SN4, PU5, PR5, PR7 were deleted from the model because their loading factors were less than 0.5 while the elimination of PE1 and PR6 were due to the absolute differences between two factor loadings was less than 0.3.

After removing eight observed variables, KMO reached 0.861 with a significance value of 0.000, showing that EFA was appropriate. Given Eigenvalue higher than 1, five factors were extracted and valid for further analysis of determinants of Vietnamese students' online shopping behavior. These factors explained more than 60.61% of the variability in the original observed variables (Table 4).

TABLE 4. TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED

FACTOR	INITIAL EIGENVALUES			EXTRACTION SUMS OF SQUARED LOADINGS		
	TOTAL	% OF VARIANCE	CUMULATIVE %	TOTAL	% OF VARIANCE	CUMULATIVE %
1	6.308	30.040	30.040	6.308	30.040	30.040
2	2.297	10.937	40.977	2.297	10.937	40.977
3	1.863	8.870	49.847	1.863	8.870	49.847
4	1.256	5.983	55.830	1.256	5.983	55.830
5	1.005	4.785	60.615	1.005	4.785	60.615
6	0.879	4.184	64.798			
7	0.804	3.829	68.627			
8	0.764	3.636	72.263			
9	0.684	3.259	75.522			
10	0.623	2.965	78.487			
11	0.574	2.735	81.222			
12	0.536	2.550	83.772			
13	0.516	2.459	86.231			
14	0.470	2.236	88.467			
15	0.461	2.195	90.662			
16	0.415	1.977	92.639			
17	0.374	1.780	94.419			
18	0.347	1.654	96.072			
19	0.291	1.387	97.459			
20	0.269	1.280	98.739			
21	0.265	1.261	100.000			

Source: SPSS results.

The results from rotation component matrix showed that there was a change in position of observed variable PU2 from factor PU to factor AT, implying that money saving when shopping online was more related to attitude of online buyers (Table 5).

TABLE 5. ROTATED COMPONENT MATRIX

VARIABLES	COMPONENT				
	1	2	3	4	5
WQ6	0.772				
WQ2	0.736				
WQ3	0.724				
WQ7	0.696				
WQ1	0.679				
WQ5	0.642				
WQ4	0.535				
AT3		0.784			
AT2		0.740			
AT4		0.737			
PU2		0.564			
PR1			0.791		
PR2			0.770		
PR3			0.769		
PR4			0.614		
PU3				0.784	
PU4				0.726	
PU1				0.569	
SN1					0.847
SN2					0.750
SN3					0.621

Source: SPSS results.

Finally, after reliability test and EFA, five factors were extracted and revised as shown in Table 6.

TABLE 6. REVISED FACTORS AFTER CRONBACH ALPHA TEST AND EFA

No.	FACTOR	OBSERVED VARIABLES	EXPLANATION
1	AT	AT3, AT2, AT4, PU2	Attitude towards online shopping
2	SN	SN1, SN2, SN3	Subjective Norm
3	PR	PR1, PR2, PR3, PR4	Perceived Risk
4	PU	PU3, PU4, PU1	Perceived Usefulness
5	WQ	WQ1, WQ2, W3, WQ4, WQ5, WQ6, WQ7	Website Quality

Source: Compiled by the authors from SPSS results.

4.4. Multiple regression analysis

The next step is to conduct multiple regression analysis to determine factors influencing online shopping behavior of university students in Vietnam.

With R-squared of 0.426, the proposed model was relatively useful when it explained 42.6% of the changes in university students' shopping behavior (Table 7). Besides, VIF of

all factors were below 2, showing that multicollinearity did not exist in the model. All factors except PR had significance levels lower than 0.05. Therefore, there is not enough statistical evidence to conclude that PR affects students' online purchasing decision. On the contrary, there is enough statistical evidence to conclude that AT, PU, SN and WQ are positively related to online shopping decisions of university students in Hanoi, Vietnam.

TABLE 7. REGRESSION ANALYSIS RESULTS

	Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Standardized Coefficients	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.329**	0.229	5.800	0.000			
AT	0.148**	0.042	3.513	0.001	0.183	0.746	1.341
PR	-0.035	0.044	-0.799	0.425	-0.037	0.935	1.070
PU	0.261**	0.051	5.133	0.000	0.299	0.596	1.677
SN	0.091*	0.042	2.158	0.032	0.112	0.756	1.323
WQ	0.240**	0.059	4.048	0.000	0.249	0.536	1.867
Dependent variable: BP							
Sample	289						
F	42.042						
R-squared	0.426						
Adjusted R-squared	0.416						

Source: SPSS results.

Note: **, *: Significance level of 1% and 5%, respectively

4.5. Independent sample test

The paper conducted independent sample test to find out whether different genders and grades have impacts on online shopping behavior of university students in Hanoi, Vietnam. The results showed that there is an insignificant difference in online shopping behavior between male and female students (Table 8), while grades of students significantly affect their online shopping behavior (Table 9). More detailed, there is a difference in shopping behavior between the first and the third-year students, and between the second and the third-year students.

TABLE 8. INDEPENDENT SAMPLES TEST FOR GENDER

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for equality of means				
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
		BP	Equal variances assumed	0.264	0.608	0.795	287	0.427
	Equal variances not assumed			0.800	259.8	0.424	0.060	0.07526

Source: SPSS results.

TABLE 9. COMPARISON SAMPLE TEST FOR GRADE

(I) Grade	(J) Compared Grade	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
First year	Second year	-0.03287	0.11757	0.780	-0.2643	0.1985
	Third year	-0.38027*	0.13852	0.006	-0.6529	-0.1076
	Fourth year	-0.27850	0.15931	0.082	-0.5921	0.0351
Second year	First year	0.03287	0.11757	0.780	-0.1985	0.2643
	Third year	-0.34740*	0.09854	0.000	-0.5414	-0.1534
	Fourth year	-0.24563	0.12611	0.052	-0.4938	0.0026
Third year	First year	0.38027*	0.13852	0.006	0.1076	0.6529
	Second year	0.34740*	0.09854	0.000	0.1534	0.5414
	Fourth year	0.10177	0.14584	0.486	-0.1853	0.3888
Fourth year	First year	0.27850	0.15931	0.082	-0.0351	0.5921
	Second year	0.24563	0.12611	0.052	-0.0026	0.4938
	Third year	-0.10177	0.14584	0.486	-0.3888	0.1853

Source: SPSS results.

4.6. Discussion

Discussion on deleted observed variables and statistically insignificant factor

Observed variable AT1 “I am not willing to search for new products on Internet” was deleted from the model in scale reliability test. This can be explained that Vietnamese students believe more in finding information about new products via different channels other than Internet such as through their families, friends, colleagues or other types of media such as television. Internet might be just a second step that students use to search for more information about new products after they consult more reliable sources.

In EFA, all variables in factor PE “Perceived Ease of Use” including PE1, PE2 and PE3 were removed. In fact, because of the universalization of Internet as well as the availability of online services, almost all university students in Vietnam have easy access to Internet and online purchasing websites. This situation might be quite different from the time when Davis (1985) considered Perceived Ease of Use as an important determinant of technological acceptance in his TAM model. For this reason, factor PE was irrelevant in the model examining Vietnamese university students’ online shopping behavior.

SN4 “Well-known brands affect me when I shop online” was also deleted in EFA step, indicating that students do not care about well-known brand when shopping online. It may be partially because of student’s limited monthly expenditure. In addition, goods and services in Vietnam’s online markets are sourced from plenty of origins and brands, and fake products for well-known brands are relatively common. As a result, students concern more about the actual product with actual usefulness, and believe more in other reference sources rather than brand when shopping online.

Three observed variables PR5, PR6 and PR7 related to Perceived Risk in terms of complaints and refunds, system errors and shipping errors were eliminated. The surveyed students said that companies undertaking online shopping in Vietnam up to now perform

relatively well in managing and tracking orders from sellers to shippers and to buyers. Thus, a product to be lost due to system or shipping error rarely happens. If this case unfortunately happens, E-commerce companies will apply their Complaints and Refund Policies to protect their customers. In addition, students also said that information availability and the rapid development of payment services contribute to reducing risks from shopping online. For above reason, students do not care much about risks related to complaints and refunds, system errors or shipping errors when shopping online. This argument is confirmed in regression analysis, by which factor PR is not significant.

Discussion on the importance of each factor on online shopping behavior of university students in Hanoi, Vietnam

Regression results show that PU “Perceived Usefulness”, WQ “Web Quality”, AT “Attitude” and SN “Subjective Norm” are four determinants of shopping online behavior of university students in Vietnam. The order of importance of each factor is illustrated in Table 10.

TABLE 10. IMPORTANCE OF EACH FACTOR

FACTOR	SIG.	STANDARDIZED BETA	ABSOLUTE BETA	CONTRIBUTION	ORDER OF IMPORTANCE
PU	0.000	0.299	0.299	35.469%	1
WQ	0.000	0.249	0.249	29.537%	2
AT	0.001	0.183	0.183	21.708%	3
SN	0.032	0.112	0.112	13.286%	4
Total			0.843	100.00%	

Source: Authors' calculations from SPSS results.

PU plays the most important role in determining students' decisions of shopping online with a contribution of 35.47% (Table 10). Among variables in this factor, a wider choice (PU3) and easy comparison of different products (PU4) are two factors student care most with factor loading of 0.784 and 0.726 respectively (Table 5 above). Moreover, saving time is also another usefulness considered by students as they do not have to take time for travelling and can stay at home to easily make purchasing decisions.

With a contribution of 29.54%, WQ ranks second in affecting purchasing decisions of university students in Vietnam (Table 10). In this factor, students pay most attention to “the ability to access to E-commerce websites through a wide range of devices” (WQ6) with the loading factor of 0.772 (Table 5 above). In fact, the rapid development of iCloud technology and different applications help synchronize multiple devices such as computers, iPads and smartphones. As a result, students care about whether a website is easier to access through different devices to facilitate their shopping. Other factors that students concern are attractive and clear illustration of products (WQ2), detailed and clear information (WQ3), and fast processing speed rate of the web (WQ1). One more point worthy commenting is that students in Vietnam also appreciate websites that are verified by Vietnam's Ministry of Industry and Trade (WQ7), showing that students are more aware of legal aspect of E-commerce.

AT contributes 21.71% in determining students' online shopping decision (Table 10). Although this factor was considered as the most important factor in some previous studies such as Thananuraksakul (2007), it just stands at the third place in our model. Students' willingness to provide personal information to sellers or intermediary websites (AT3), their trust in E-commerce (AT2) and willingness to make payment in advance (AT4) are three factors promoting them to have good attitude towards online shopping and eventually decide to purchase online.

SN contributes 13.29% in determining students' online shopping behavior. Friends and colleagues (SN1) affect students most when they implement a buying transaction online with a factor loading of 0.874 (Table 5 above). Family and relatives' opinions (SN2) are the second most important source students concern. The results also showed that students pay least attention to online comments on the products they intend to buy (SN3). It might be due to the increase in fake comments in a lot of online E-commerce websites and social networks in Vietnam, especially those conducted by private sellers and unverified by Vietnam's Ministry of Industry and Trade.

Finally, independent sample test results pointed out that the third-year students tend to enjoy and take online shopping more than the first and second-year students. Students in the third year also have stronger belief in development trend of E-commerce. It can be explained by the fact that a large proportion of students in Hanoi, Vietnam start to work part time in the third year, and therefore have higher income and afford more their daily consumption. In addition, at the third year, students have more knowledge and skills, making them more confident in taking online shopping activities.

References

- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179-211.
- Balfour, F. (2008, June 17). In Vietnam, eBay Finds a Partner. *Bloomberg*. Retrieved March 15, 2018, from <https://www.bloomberg.com>
- Bhatnagar, A., Misra, S., & Rao, H. R. (2000). On risk, convenience, and Internet shopping behavior. *Communications of the ACM*, 43(11), 98-105.
- Chang, M., Cheung, W., & Lai, V. (2005). Literature derived reference models for the adoption of online shopping. *Information & Management*, 42(4), 543-559.
- Cox, D. F., & Rich, S. U. (1964). Perceived Risk and Consumer Decision-Making: The Case of Telephone Shopping. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 1(4), 32-39.
- Dang, T. T. D. (2014). *Studying factors influencing online shopping intention of customers in Da Nang city*. Master Thesis, Da Nang University.
- David, F. D. (1985). *A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end-user information systems: Theory and results*. Doctoral dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319-340.
- Duong, T. H. P. (2012). Studying factors influencing online shopping intention of customers in Hue City. *Journal of Science*, 72B(3), 263-274.
- EVBN. (2018). *E-Commerce Industry in Vietnam: Edition 2018*. Vietnam: EU - Vietnam Business Network.

- Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975). *Beleif, attitude, intention and behavior: An introduction to theory and research*. MA: Addison - Wesley.
- Gefen, D., & Straub, D. (2000). The relative importance of perceived ease of use in IS adoption: A study of E-commerce adoption. *Journal of Association for Information System*, 1(8), 1-28.
- Ha, N. T., & Nguyen, T. D. (2016). Factors influencing Vietnamese consumers' online shopping intention: An extension of the Theory of Planned Behavior. *VNU Journal of Science - Economics and Business*, 32(4), 21-28.
- Hansen, T., Møller Jensen, J., & Solgaard, H. S. (2004). Predicting online grocery buying intention: a comparison of the theory of reasoned action and the theory of planned behavior. *International Journal of Information Management*, 24(6), 539-550.
- Helander, M. G., & Khalid, H. M. (2000). Modeling the customer in electronic commerce. *Applied Ergonomics*, 31(6), 609-619.
- Hoffman, D. L., Novak, T. P., & Peralta, M. (1999). Building consumer trust online. *Communications of the ACM*, 42(4), 80-85.
- Iprice Insights. (2017). *The state of eCommerce in Southeast Asia 2017: White paper*. Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia: Iprice Insights.
- Jadhav, V., & Khanna, M. (2016). Factors Influencing Online Buying Behavior of College Students: A Qualitative Analysis. *The Qualitative Report*, 21(1), 1-15.
- Kemp, P. (2018). Digital in 2018: World's internet users pass the 4 billion mark. Retrieved March 15, 2018, from <https://wearesocial.com/>.
- Khare, A., & Rakesh, S. (2011). Antecedents of Online Shopping Behavior in India: An Examination. *Journal of Internet Commerce*, 10(4), 227-244.
- Kim, D. J., Ferrin, D. L., & Rao, H. R. (2008). A trust-based consumer decision-making model in electronic commerce: The role of trust, perceived risk, and their antecedents. *Decision Support Systems*, 44(2), 544-564.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2006). *Marketing management* (12th ed). Upper Saddle River, N.J: Pearson/Prentice Hall.
- Koufaris, M., (2002). Applying the Technology Acceptance Model and Flow Theory to Online Consumer Behavior. *Information Systems Research*, 13(2), 205-223.
- Lee, D., Park, J., & Ahn, J.H. (2001). *On the Explanation of Factors Affecting E-Commerce Adoption*. Paper in International Conference on Information Systems, New Orleans, Louisiana, the US.
- Li, N., & Zhang, P. (2002) Consumer online shopping attitudes and behavior: an assessment of research. *Americas Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS) Proceedings and AIS Electronic Library (AISel)*, 508-517.
- Limayem, M., Khalifa, M., & Frini, A. (2000). What makes consumers buy from Internet? A longitudinal study of online shopping. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics - Part A: Systems and Humans*, 30(4), 421-432.
- Loudon, D. L., & Bitta, A. J. D. (1993). *Consumer Behaviour Concepts and Applications* (4th ed). New York: McGraw-Hill
- Minh, T. (2017, October 6). Alibaba extends business in Vietnam. *Vietnam Forbes*. Retrieved February 10, 2018, from <https://forbesvietnam.com.vn/>
- Moon, J.W., & Kim, Y. G. (2001). Extending the TAM for a World-Wide-Web context. *Information & Management*, 38(4), 217-230.

- Mudambi, S. M., & Schuff, D. (2010). What makes a helpful online review? A study of customer reviews on amazon.com. *MIS Quarterly*, 34(1), 185-200.
- Ngo, T. V. K., & Gim, G. (2014). Factors affecting the online shopping behavior: An empirical investigation in Vietnam. *Journal of Engineering Research and Applications*, 4(2), 388-392.
- Nguyen, T. B. C., & Le, X. D. (2014). Analysing factors affecting online shopping behavior of consumers in Can Tho city. *Can Tho University Journal of Science*, 30 (2014), 8-14.
- Peterson, R. A. (1994). A Meta-Analysis of Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 21(2), 381-391.
- Slater, S. F. (1995). Issues in conducting marketing strategy research. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 3(4), 257-270.
- Smith, A. D., & Rupp, W. T. (2003). Strategic online customer decision making: leveraging the transformational power of the Internet. *Online Information Review*, 27(6), 418-432.
- Song, J., & Zahedi, F. (2001). *Web design in e-commerce: a theory and empirical analysis*. Papers in International Conference on Information System, New Orleans, Louisiana, the USA.
- Teo, T. S. H. (2002). Attitudes toward online shopping and the Internet. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 21(4), 259-271.
- Thananuraksakul, S. (2007). *Factors effecting online shopping behaviour: A study of Thai consumers*. Doctor desertation of Business Administration, University of South Australia.
- Tran, P. H., Nguyen T. V., Luong, T. M. H., & Phan, T. H. V. (2015). The factors affecting the decision to shop online of Vietnamese youth in fashion field. *International Journal of Research in Finance and Marketing*, 5(11), 64-73.
- Tran, V. N., Tarofder, A. K., & Azam, F. S. M. (2017). Factors influencing online shopping trial decision in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. *European Journal of Social Sciences Studies*, 2(8), 330-356.
- VECITA. (2017). *Vietnam's E-commerce Report 2017*. Retrieved March 1, 2018, from Vietnam E-commerce and Communication Technology Agency website: <http://www.idea.gov.vn/>
- VECOM. (2012 June 15). Google officially became a member of VECOM. Retrieved February 3, 2017, from <http://www.vecom.vn/>
- VECOM. (2016). *Vietnam E-business Index: EBI 2015*. Vietnam: Vietnam E-Commerce Association.
- VECOM. (2018). *Vietnam E-business Index: EBI 2018*. Vietnam: Vietnam E-commerce Association.
- Vo, T. H., & Han, K. S. (2017). Affection of Vietnamese social network on e-commerce behaviors. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 6(5), 1-11.
- VSEC. (2017). Current status of information security in e-commerce in Vietnam. *Blogen*. Retrieved March 1, 2018, from <https://vsec.com.vn/>
- Xu, Y., & Paulins, V. A. (2005). College students' attitudes toward shopping online for apparel products. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*, 9(4), 420-433.
- Zhang, P., & Dran, V.G. M. (2000). Satisfiers and dissatisfiers: A two-factor model for website design and evaluation. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 51(14), 1253-1268.